

Potassium fertilizer experiments in farmer fields

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We studied rice response to potash application on farmer fields in Dera Ismail Khan district of the North West Frontier Province of Pakistan. Available potash at different sites was 100 to 250 ppm, and chloride content was 28 to 39 ppm. In the first experiment (Table 1) all levels of applied potash increased rice yields significantly. Some benefits may have been derived from K application.

In the second experiment, application of 135-40-37 kg NPK/ha produced the highest yield of 7.58 t/ha (Table 2).

Of two K sources (Table 2), K_2SO_4 was significantly better than KCl. □

Table 1. Effect of K application on paddy yield, Tarnab, Pakistan.^a

Treatment (kg/ha)			Yield ^b (t/ha)	Increase over N + P (t/ha)
N	P	K		
0	0	0	3.57 b	—
120	40	0	5.05 a	—
120	40	25	5.19 a	0.14
120	40	50	5.65 a	0.60
120	40	15	5.97 a	0.92
120	40	100	5.72 a	0.67
120	40	125	5.58 a	0.53

^a As of 5 experiments in 1979-81. ^b Separation of means by Duncan's Multiple Range Test at 5% level.

Table 2. Effect of fertilizer applications on paddy yield. Tarnab, Pakistan.

Treatment (kg/ha)			Yield ^a (t/ha)	Increase over N + P (t/ha)	Value of increased yield ^b (US\$)	Value-cost ^c ratio
N	P	K				
<i>NPK application^d</i>						
0	0	0	4.95 c	—	—	—
135	0	0	6.07 b	—	—	—
135	40	0	6.97 ab	—	—	—
135	40	37	7.58 a	0.61	74.20	12.97
<i>K₂SO₄ and KCl application^e</i>						
120	35	0	4.91 c	—	—	—
120	35	83 (KCl)	5.52 b	0.61	74.72	9.34
120	35	83 (K ₂ SO ₄)	6.11 a	1.21	148.22	12.35

^a Separation of means by Duncan's multiple range test at 5% level. ^b Value of paddy = US\$122.5/t.

^c Fertilizer cost = K_2SO_4 : US\$12/83 kg K, US\$ = 8/83 kg K. Value-cost ratio is for KCl:potash only.

^d Av of 3 experiments in 1979-81. ^e Av of 25 experiments in 1979-81.

Dual cropping azolla in lowland rice

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We evaluated azolla as a substitute for N fertilizer for lowland rice IR20 in the field at TNRRI in winter 1982-83. The soil had pH 6.8 with CEC 24.5 meq/100 g and 5.9 ppm available P (Olsen), dry soil basis. Eighty kg P and 31 kg potash/ha were applied basally.

Azolla was inoculated with 30 and 60 kg N/ha and results were compared with four N treatments (see table). Urea N was applied 50% basally and in 2 equal splits 20 and 40 d after transplanting, and 500 kg fresh *Azolla pinnata*/ha was applied 1 wk after

Effect of azolla on grain yield of IR20, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
No N control	2.8
30	3.2
60	3.7
90 N	3.9
30 N + azolla	3.7
60 N + azolla	3.9
LSD (0.05)	
	0.7

transplanting. Azolla was allowed to multiply and decompose in the field. A maximum biomass of 790 g/m² was recorded at a multiplication rate of 195 g/m² per week. N content of fresh azolla was 0.37%.

Dual cropping 500 kg fresh azolla/ha with 60 kg N gave a yield equal to that with 90 kg N (see table). □

Environment and its influence

Screening for shade tolerance in rice seedlings

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Rice plants are subjected to various degrees of low light intensity when grown under coconut trees, in pockets of forest land, when mixed with other crops, and when grown during the wet

season. Rice production in these situations is poor because solar radiation for crop growth is insufficient. Some degree of shade tolerance may overcome this situation. We sought to determine suitable morphological and physiological parameters to use in screening for shade tolerance and to develop a suitable screening method for use in the greenhouse.

Ten pregerminated seeds of 10 varieties were sown in a row in each 40 × 25 × 15-cm plastic tray filled with 6 cm of

fine Maahas clay. The experiment was in three replications. For 14 d, the 10-d-old seedlings were subjected to 3 degrees of shading: 55, 72, and 86%. Two sets were given continuous dark treatment for 7 or 14 d.

Plants grown in 55% shade produced 50% less dry weight than those in full sun. Fifty-five percent shading was judged to be critical. IR52 and FR13A showed the least reduction in dry matter at that level (see table). At the end of

the treatment, Leb Mue Nahng 111, Kurkaruppan, Nam Sagui 19, and FR13A had the highest dry weight and highest leaf area per plant. Based on dry matter produced, those four varieties should perform well in the shade. FR13A and Kurkaruppan also show the least reduction in plant weight at higher degrees of shading.

A set of plants was placed in total darkness for 7 d to test if this could be a faster way of screening for shade tolerance. Generally, the varieties with high dry matter weight at 55% shading had high survival rate in complete darkness ($r = 0.578^*$). The correlation, however is not very high and screening at 55% shading would be a better method.

Thin leaves or low specific leaf

Effect of shade on rice seedlings.^a

Variety	Dry matter (mg/plant) at 55% shade	Decrease (%) in dry matter at 55% shade	Leaf area (cm ²) /plant at 55% shade	SLW ^b (mg/dm ²) in normal light	Survival (%) at 7 d darkness				
IR1529-680-3-2	125	ef	56 a	28.75	g	3.27 a	37	bcd	
IR52	156	de	39 b	39.42	ef	2.10	de	83 a	
RD19	180	cd	52 ab	44.02	de	1.97	e	93 a	
Thavalu (acc. 15314)	176	cd	54 a	34.70	f	2.91	b	70 abc	
Leb Mue Nahng 111	213	bc	58 a	48.73	cd	2.55	c	63 abc	
Kurkaruppan	233	ab	58 a	57.87	b	2.52	c	83 ab	
Nam Sagui	226	ab	55 a	54.30	bc	2.31	cde	40 bcd	
FR13A	263	a	42 ab	68.00	a	2.27	cde	73 abc	
IR42	104	f	50 ab	27.07	gh	2.37	cd	27	cd
IR20	91	f	57 a	21.67	h	2.33	cde	30	cd

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b Specific leaf weight.

weight (SLW), said to be characteristic of varieties suitable for low light intensities, is found in FR13A, IR52, and RD19. Growing the varieties to maturity

to obtain grain yield would give the ultimate measure of their shade tolerance. Further studies, using more varieties, need to be made. □

Cropping systems

Potential of rice-based multiple cropping sequences for irrigated conditions in Uttar Pradesh

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Rice is the predominant crop in most medium-altitude irrigated valleys in the UP hills. The most popular crop rotations are rice (Jun-Oct) – wheat (Nov-May) and rice (Jul-Oct) – potato (Feb-Jun), with an intervening fallow period from late Oct to mid-Feb. Cropping intensity is restricted to 200%.

We conducted a fixed plot field study from 1978 to 1981 at the VPKAS experimental farms, Hawalbagh, to determine ways of increasing cropping intensity. Four crop sequences with 34 crops/year were compared with the popular 2 crop rice – wheat rotation. Data for the rice – potato rotation were also compiled.

Short-duration varieties were used in the intensive cropping sequences and medium-duration varieties were planted in the less intensive sequences. Recommended cultural practices were adopted

Yield, costs, and returns in 1978–81 for irrigated rice-based cropping systems in UP, India.

Cropping pattern	Yield (t/ha)	Total variable cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
Rice (VL Dhan 8) - wheat (VL Gehun 421)	4.7	497	630	2.4
Rice (VLK Dhan 39) - rapeseed (T9) - potato (K. Jeoti)	5.1	988	1,019	2.1
Rice (VLK Dhan 39) - cabbage (Golden acre) - maize for green cobs (VL Makka 16)	3.9	940	1,485	2.6
Rice (VLK Dhan 39) - radish (Japanese white long) - pea (vegetable pod Arkel) - French bean (vegetable pod) VL Bauni 1	37.4	62,666 ^a		
Rice (VLK Dhan 39) - radish (Japanese white long) - pea (vegetable pod Arkel) - French bean (vegetable pod) VL Bauni 1	3.7	854	1,456	2.7

^a Number of cobs.

for all crops.

Highest average annual net returns were from a rice – cabbage – maize (green cobs) rotation followed by rice – radish – pea (vegetable) – French bean (vegetable) and rice – rapeseed (*Brassica campestris* L. var. *toria*) – potato sequences. Rice – wheat yielded the lowest net return (see table).

From the benefit-cost ratio point of view, the rice – radish – pea (vegetable)

– French bean (vegetable) sequence was best, followed by rice – cabbage – maize (green cobs). However, these sequences can be adopted only near marketplaces because vegetables are an important component. In places away from marketing centers, rice – rapeseed – potato can be adopted to increase profits. This pattern is being adopted by some cultivators. □